

**THE PRINCIPLE OF JUDICIAL TRUTH IN CIVIL
PROCESS OF UZBEKISTAN**

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According to the article 15 of the Code of Civil Procedure of Uzbekistan, the court, not being limited to the presented materials and explanations, shall have the right to take measures in accordance with the law for full, complete and objective clarification of the real circumstances of the case, rights and obligations of the parties.

The court shall explain to persons participating in the case their rights and obligations, warn of the consequences of the commission or failure to commit of procedural actions and assist persons participating in the case in exercising their rights [1].

The content of this principle includes the provision that the court should take measures to determine the actual circumstances, clearly define the relations between the parties, and that the court's decision should be based on the facts that have been verified and clearly proven by all parties at the court session.

In order to objectively determine the truth of the case, the court should assist the parties involved in explaining their rights and duties.

The Civil procedural law of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at determining the actual situation of the civil case, regardless of the different forms, which in turn is the practical manifestation of the principle aimed at solving the case objectively. This rule applies to all stages of the civil process [2].

Persons participating in the case exercise their procedural rights and procedural duties by performing appropriate procedural actions. In order to determine the true circumstances of the case, the court performs a number of procedural actions, for example, each party submits evidence justifying its demands and objections, if necessary, recommends the presentation of additional evidence to determine the true circumstances of the case, and provides assistance to the parties in their collection.

During the hearing of the case, according to the general rule, the court must inform the parties about the time and place of the hearing of the case in order to determine the truth. It provides an opportunity to protect their rights at the court session, make a statement, get acquainted with the case materials, present evidence, object to the other side, and prove their claim requirements, including the objection related to the claim, with relevant evidence.

After acceptance of the claim and rendering the ruling on institution of the case, the judge shall prepare the case for court trial in order to ensure timely and proper consideration and resolution of the case. The objectives of preparation of civil cases for court trial shall be as follows:

- Defining the legal relations of the parties and the law to be guided by;
- Specifying the facts that justify the claims and objections of the parties, as well as other facts relevant to the proper resolution of the dispute;
- Defining the range of evidence required to resolve the case and ensuring its timely presentation for the court hearing;
- Resolving the issue of the possible composition of persons participating in the case;
- Presentation of necessary evidence by the parties and other persons participating in the case;
- Conciliation of parties.

If necessary, when preparing a case for court trial, the judge may interview the parties. In so doing, the judge shall:

- 1) Interview the plaintiff on the merits of the claims asserted by him/her; clarify with him/her possible objections on the part of defendant; and, if necessary, invite the plaintiff to present additional evidence; as well as clarify the right to waive the asserted claims and legal implications thereof;
- 2) Interview the defendant about the circumstances of the case; clarify his/her objections to the claims of the plaintiff and evidence these objections can be confirmed by; as well as clarify the defendant's right to recognize the claims of the plaintiff or to make counterclaims; and invite the defendant to provide written explanations on the case in particularly complex cases. The defendant's failure to provide written explanations and evidence in case of his/her failure to appear in court shall not hinder the consideration of the case on the evidence available in the case;
- 3) Determine the possibility of concluding a settlement agreement or mediation agreement between the parties and explain their legal consequences.

The judge shall perform the following actions in order to prepare the case for court trial:

- 1) Resolve the issue of involving or joining the case of third parties and interview the third parties allowed to participate in the case, who make individual claims;
- 2) Resolve the issue of representatives' intervention in the case;

- 3) Resolve the issue of prosecutor's participation in the case and involvement of the relevant State administration body in the court proceedings;
- 4) Resolve the issue of joining the case of co-plaintiffs, co-defendants and third parties, as well as resolve the issue of replacing the improper defendant,
- 5) Resolve the issue of summoning witnesses to the court session;
- 6) Reclaim written and physical evidence from organizations or citizens or issue requests for such evidence to persons participating in the case for submission to the court;
- 7) Resolve — taking into account the opinion of the persons participating in the case — the issue of appointing an expert and engaging a specialist;
- 8) In urgent cases, carry out on-site inspection with notifying the persons participating in the case;
- 9) Send letters of request to other courts;
- 10) Explain to the persons participating in the case their procedural rights and obligations;
- 11) Resolve the issue of combining similar cases and disconnection of several claims into separate proceedings;
- 12) Resolve the issue of securing of suit and securing of evidence;
- 13) Take measures to reconcile the parties;
- 14) Resolve the issue of holding a court session by videoconferencing and explain to the persons participating in the case their right to participate in the court session.

The judge shall also perform other procedural actions to prepare the case for court trial. Actions of the judge to prepare the case for court trial shall be formalized through the judge's ruling without summoning the persons participating in the case.

The judge, having recognized the case as sufficiently prepared, shall render a ruling on its assignment for trial in the court session and take measures to notify the parties and other participants of the court proceedings about the time and place of consideration of the case.

The presiding judge shall explain to the persons participating in the case their procedural rights and obligations, which shall be indicated in the trial record.

According to the article 72 of the Code of Civil Procedure of Uzbekistan, each party shall be obliged to prove the circumstances to which it refers as the basis for its claims and objections.

The court shall determine the circumstances of relevance to the case and the parties to be proved and shall put them on the table even if the parties have not referred to them.

The evidence shall be presented by the parties and the other persons participating in the case. The court may invite them to present additional evidence. Where it is difficult for the parties and other persons participating in the case to present additional evidence, the court shall assist them at their request in the collection of evidence.

As we can see from the above rules, judges play an active role in conducting civil court cases. It is related to the Soviet-era influence on Uzbekistan's civil procedure legislation. A similar provision can be found in the Civil Procedure Code, which was adopted on March 23, 1963, and came into effect on January 1, 1964 [3]. In contrast to the current code, the 1963 code defines procedural actions, such as gathering evidence to determine the true state of the case, as part of the judge's duty and obligation. In the Civil Procedure Code adopted on August 30, 1997 and implemented from January 1, 1998, this rule (Article 15) was defined as a right, not an obligation of the court.

However, as a result of judicial reforms carried out in recent years, special attention has been paid to strengthening the role of the parties in court proceedings. In particular, it is indicated as a special task to strengthen the adversarial principle in the resolution of court cases. The adversarial principle is one of the important principles of civil process, and strengthening the practical implementation of this principle is one of the main goals of the reforms implemented in the field of judiciary in our country. Strengthening the comprehensive implementation of this principle is also in the second direction of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, called "Priority directions for ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial system" [4].

As a logical continuation of these reforms, and as the second direction of the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, it was emphasized that in order to achieve justice and the rule of law, it is necessary to realize the principles of real equality and adversary of the parties in court proceedings [5]. Nowadays, scholars of civil procedure have an important task of clarifying the relationship between the adversarial principle and the principle of determining the objective truth in civil procedure. Recently, the nature of the truth established in civil proceedings (objective, legal, relative, formal or judicial) is the subject of discussions. It should be noted that at different times the concept

of objective truth was understood differently. In Soviet jurisprudence, objective truth rightfully played the role of the goal of civil proceedings. However, in the textbook of Kleinman A.F. (1954), objective truth is positioned as the most important of the principles of civil justice: "... the principle of objective truth is that the court, when trying and resolving a case, should aim to establish the actual circumstances that took place in reality, should strive in every possible way to clarify the actual relationship of the parties, and the judicial decision should be based on reliably established, proven circumstances of the case"[6]. But there is no definition or specification of the principle of objective truth in modern legislation.

In the post-Soviet period, civil procedural legislation was significantly reformed in the direction of changing the roles of the court and the parties and increasing the activity of participants in the proceedings. In accordance with the previously functioning procedural norms, the adversarial principle in civil proceedings was "smoothed out" by the official recognition of the task of establishing objective truth and the active role of the court in the process.

Throughout history, people have tried to find a definition of truth. Due to a lack of understanding of how to resolve the dispute, inquisitorial solutions dominated for many centuries. So what should be the adversarial process in order to establish the truth in the case? Or is the real achievement of the truth not at all the goal of an adversarial trial? The spread of ideas about the truth in the adversarial process in the modern science of civil and arbitration process is quite wide. So, Reznichenko I.M. notes: "The latest civil procedural legislation demonstrates the evolution of the principle of objective truth ... to the principle of formal truth". The role of the court, according to the author, is now limited to the triad: creation of conditions for a comprehensive and complete investigation of the circumstances of the case; explaining to the participants of the process their rights and obligations and assistance in exercising their rights [7].

According to Ageeva Yu., the strengthening of the adversarial principle of civil proceedings makes it difficult to establish the actual circumstances of the case, since each of the parties is more inclined to a satisfactory outcome of the case than to establishing the truth, but adversarialism is not an alternative to objective truth, but, on the contrary, the adversarial principle and objective truth are interdependent and complement each other [8].

Only if earlier competition was of secondary importance in achieving the truth, and the main role was assigned to the court, now, as Bonner notes, the methods of achieving truth in court have changed. In the modern process, the

competitiveness of legal proceedings should become the main tool for establishing the truth in justice. Bonner A.T. confirms his position, expressed earlier, that the principle of objective truth exists, he calls it the principle of “objective (judicial) truth” [9].

From the above, it can be concluded that, in order to fulfill the task of establishing objective truth, the civil court needs the following functions:

Direct active participation of the court in the collection of evidence,

Direct examination of evidence by the court,

Autonomous and impartial evaluation of evidence by the court,

Issuance of a court decision based on the presented and confirmed evidence.

Having said that, it is important to keep in mind that today's courts are capable of performing all the functions that are necessary to establish objective truth. However, the adversarial principle and the role of objective truth in the process of administering justice remains unclear. Despite the fact that scientific disputes about objective truth do not fade today, this topic continues to be important for advancing the science of civil procedure.

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